

THE CONCEPT AND CHARACTERISTICS OF PUBLIC SERVICES AND CIVIL-LEGAL SERVICES

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Annotation. This article analyzes the concept of the provision of public services, their fundamental difference from civil law services provided to legal entities and individuals by state bodies authorized to provide certain services. In addition, it was noted that as a result of the provision of public services, interested persons acquire an administrative act of administrative bodies.

Keywords: public services, proactive, composite, procedure, transparent, administrative regulation, electronic services, traditional services, center, electronic portal, electronic document, electronic service, traditional service.

The creation of a system for providing public services to the population and entrepreneurs in our country is closely linked to the implementation of priority areas of administrative reforms, as well as the fulfillment of the ambitious and important tasks set before us to deepen democratic reforms.

The creation of such a system is a testament to the implementation of the principle that "the people should serve the state bodies, not the state bodies" should become the main rule in the activities of leaders at all levels.

In forming the system of providing public services to the population and entrepreneurs, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, in his speech at the solemn ceremony dedicated to the 25th anniversary of the adoption of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan on December 7, 2017, stated: "Today, the trust of our population in the Public Reception Centers is growing. The role of these structures in increasing the responsibility of officials of state bodies is becoming more and more noticeable. We all understand well that as the standard of living of our people increases and many problems are resolved, the number of applications to the Public Reception Centers decreases. Therefore, we will direct the capabilities of these reception centers to the provision of public services." [1].

The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-5278 dated December 12, 2017 “On measures to radically reform the national system of providing public services to the population” along with the factors for the formation of the public service system, the history and trends of the formation of this system, including the fact that since 2003, registration of business entities on the “single window” principle has been carried out by the business registration inspections under the district (city) khokimiyats, since January 1, 2016, unified centers for providing public services to business entities on the “single window” principle have been established on the basis of the Inspections, and from February 1, 2017, the transfer of the unified centers from the structure of district (city) khokimiyats to the jurisdiction of the Ministry of Justice of the Republic of Uzbekistan is the next step in the development of this area. As a result of the formation of vertical management and the organization of their effective activities, the number of public services provided by public service centers has increased to 356 today. In the 1st quarter of 2024, 7.9 million public services were provided through the Centers, of which about 5.6 million were provided through the Centers, and more than 2.3 million were provided online.

at the same time, some systemic problems are also highlighted that prevent the national system of public service provision from moving to a qualitatively new level that fully meets the needs of the population and business entities. In particular, citizens are still forced to go through complex procedures for issuing documents in various state bodies;

the lack of information systems, resources and databases in a number of state bodies, their low level of interdepartmental integration, does not ensure convenient and timely use of the entire range of state services by individuals and legal entities;

the procedures for providing most public services are complex and difficult to use, the mechanisms for pricing are not transparent, and in some cases, requirements for providing "monopoly" services are set in favor of narrow departmental interests;

the low level of implementation of information and communication technologies, the preserved patterns of paper document circulation, lead to unreasonable financial costs, long waiting times for citizens and the formation of queues, and, as a result, in some cases, to corruption and bureaucracy;

the lack of an effective system for monitoring and assessing the quality of public service delivery, including through real-time remote monitoring and public opinion surveys.

The above-mentioned factors did not allow the population to ensure widespread use of public services, reduce the time and financial costs associated with their provision, and increase the level of satisfaction of the population with the activities of state bodies, which led to the transition to a new modern system of providing public services to the population and business entities.

Since there is no law on administrative procedures in Russia, the provision of public services is regulated by administrative regulations. Accordingly, some of our experts A. Musaev include the provision of public services within the scope of administrative procedures [2, P.173].

I.A. Khamedov defined public services as “public services are actions of a presentation nature, performed by authorized bodies and organizations on behalf of the state in relation to specific interested persons, in the interests of these persons or in compliance with the public order established by law, in the form of providing information, material or immaterial interests, rights and privileges, as well as documents of legal significance, expressing the functions and public orientation of state administration” [3, P.20].

J. Nematov, on the other hand, argues that administrative procedures and public services differ sharply in their content and scope, that administrative procedures can include "executive and regulatory activities of authorized bodies and organizations of an undesirable nature for the addressee", while public services cannot include such activities, and that, in his opinion, public services and administrative procedures should be distinguished from each other. He argues that the provision of public services can be viewed in a certain sense as separate or special (sub)institutions or part of (sub)institutions of administrative procedures. [4, P.12-27].

The modern system of public service provision is aimed at regulating social relations related to the provision of public services to the population and is the integrity of the principles of governance, decision-making methods, and assigned tasks and functions of the structures established to manage this sector.

To provide effective public services, the Ministry of Justice carries out the following tasks.

1) implementation of a unified state policy in the field of providing public services to individuals and legal entities;

2) improvement of the procedure for providing public services by eliminating

unnecessary administrative procedures, as well as development of interdepartmental electronic cooperation;

3) formation of a unified register of public services, coordination of the activities of state bodies and other organizations in this area;

4) participate in the development of unified approaches to the design, development, implementation and integration of information systems, resources and databases used in the provision of public services;

5) monitor and evaluate the effectiveness of the activities of state bodies and other organizations in the field of public services, including the implementation of relevant information systems, resources and databases;

6) organize the introduction of innovative forms and methods of providing public services, develop proposals for improving legislation and law enforcement practice in this area.

The administrative reforms implemented in the system of providing public services serve to implement the noble principle that "the people should serve the public, not the public agencies," to rid the public administration system of bureaucracy and increase the efficiency and transparency of the management decision-making system, to introduce a system of innovative ideas, developments and technologies, primarily aimed at preventing corruption, to guarantee the efficiency of public service provision by improving the "Electronic Government" system, and most importantly, to ensure the rule of law in society, strengthen legality and law and order.

Although no separate law has been adopted on the provision of public services, the concept of public service provision is set out in the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Administrative Procedures" and administrative regulations for each area of public service provision.

Considering that the provision of public services is an administrative procedure, in accordance with Article 3 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Administrative Procedures", this Law applies to the administrative and legal activities of administrative bodies in relation to interested persons, including the procedures for issuing licenses, permits, registration, other procedures related to the provision of public services, as well as other administrative and legal activities in accordance with legislative acts.

Therefore, the processes of licensing, permitting, registration, and provision of public services are considered administrative procedures. At the same time, this law also

regulates relations related to the provision of public services.

The concept of providing public services differs from the concept of civil service.

According to Article 1 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, citizens (individuals) and legal entities shall have their civil rights in accordance with their will and shall exercise these rights in their own interests. They shall be free to determine their rights and obligations on a contractual basis and to determine the terms of any contract that does not contradict the law.

Article 3 of this Code states that civil legislation determines the legal status of participants in civil transactions, the grounds for the emergence of property rights and other material rights, rights to the results of intellectual activity, and the procedure for their exercise, and regulates contractual obligations and other obligations, as well as other property and related personal non-property relations.

Therefore, when receiving civil legal services, legal entities and individuals have civil rights in accordance with their will and exercise these rights in their own interests. They are also free to determine their rights and obligations on a contractual basis and to determine the terms of any contract that does not contradict the law.

Civil legal services are created through transactions and actions, as defined in civil legislation, with the participation of individuals, legal entities and the state. The provision of such services is based on the equality of the parties. In civil legal services, a transaction is concluded if the two parties reach an agreement.

Public services are fundamentally different from civil legal services. Of course, these services are provided to legal entities and individuals by state bodies authorized to provide this or that service.

The person to whom the administrative document or administrative action being adopted is addressed, as well as the person whose rights and legitimate interests are or may be affected by the administrative document or administrative action, ultimately becomes the subject of an administrative document of an administrative body aimed at establishing, changing or terminating public legal relations and having certain legal consequences for individual individuals or legal entities or for a group of persons distinguished by certain personal characteristics.

Thus, as a result of the provision of public services, interested persons receive an administrative document from administrative bodies.

Types of public services can be listed as follows.

The purpose of dividing service into forms	Service types
At the applicants' expense	Free - the legislation stipulates that such services are provided free of charge. Paid - the legislation specifies the amount for receiving such services.
By complexity	Simple service - implies the provision of one public service. Complex service - includes several public services.
In order of service	In the traditional way, through public service centers, electronically through the single public services portal.
By the nature of the relationship between the applicant and the service provider	Simple services provided by a single authority. Composite and interagency and proactive services provided by multiple authorities.
By result	1) exercising the rights of citizens as stipulated in the constitution; 2) allowing service recipients to ensure the fulfillment of their obligations under the law 3) which fulfills the legitimate interests of service recipients.

The provision of public services is the activity of bodies authorized to provide public services to implement the functions related to the provision of public services established by law, at the request of service recipients, within the limits of regulatory legal acts.

— Considering public services as an element of the public administration system, public services can ultimately be divided into the following characteristics.

- this is the activity of authorized bodies to implement specific functions;
- such activities are carried out at the request of applicants;
- executives have limits on their powers established in regulatory legal acts on the provision of public services;
- this activity is related to the implementation of the rights and obligations of applicants.

The staff of the executive bodies of public service applications includes employees of authorized bodies tasked with carrying out work related to the provision of public services.

The applicant or service recipient is also another party in the provision of public

services. The applicant is an individual or legal entity, as well as their authorized representatives, who apply to authorized state bodies through State Service Centers or the Unified Interactive State Services Portal in order to receive public services.

Authorized representatives may participate in receiving public services on behalf of the applicant through a power of attorney issued in accordance with the requirements of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

In the process of receiving state services, along with citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan, foreign citizens can also participate.

The legislation stipulates that only citizens of Uzbekistan can participate in receiving certain services. For example, when obtaining a passport or ID card for traveling abroad.

The age for receiving state services begins at the birth of a child. However, in some cases, such services (birth certificate, placement in the MTN, registration) are received by the legal representatives of the minor. Independent receipt of state services is carried out after the child reaches adulthood.

The rights and obligations of entities participating in the process of providing public services (service providers and service recipients) are determined by legislation.

The following rights and obligations of service providers are specified in the legislation: to resolve appeals within the time limit established in the legal act regulating the provision of public services, not to directly provide services provided through public service centers, not to require documents not specified in the legislation, not to reject appeals on grounds not specified in the legislation.

The rights and obligations of service recipients are also specified in legal documents. That is, to provide the specified documents to receive a public service, to pay the specified fee and duty for the public service, and to refuse to use the public service at any stage of its provision.

Therefore, the provision of public services is the activity of bodies authorized to provide public services to implement the functions related to the provision of public services established by law, at the request of service recipients, within the limits of regulatory legal acts.

The public service delivery system is the orderly and systematic activities of the authorized bodies in the field of public service delivery and the body authorized to coordinate their public service activities.

From this it follows that the social relations and norms regulating the provision of

civil legal services and state services are fundamentally different from each other, which means that civil legal services arise and are terminated on the basis of equality of the parties. State services, on the other hand, are a form of implementation of functions and tasks belonging to the state by state bodies, and these services are provided directly by state bodies.

References:

1. Speech by President Shavkat Mirziyoyev at the solemn ceremony dedicated to the 25th anniversary of the adoption of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan. <https://president.uz/uz/lists/view/1328>.
2. Musaev A. Legislation on administrative sudoproizvodstve in the Republic of Uzbekistan // Ejegodnik publichnogo prava 2015: Administrativnyy protsess. - M.: Infotropic Media, 2015. - P. 173.
3. Khamedov I.A On the issue of the concept and inventory of public services in the Republic of Uzbekistan//High training courses of the GPO.-2016.-№ 2 (26).-P. 20.
4. Nematov J.N. SCIENTIFIC AND THEORETICAL ANALYSIS OF ADMINISTRATIVE PROCEDURES AS AN INSTITUTE OF LAW. Journal of Law Research. 2019, 7 vol., issue 1, pp. 12-27
5. Abdusamatov, K., Babajanova, D., Egamberdiev, D., Xodjiyev, Y., Tukhtaev, U., Yusupov, N., & Shoislomova, S. (2024). Challenges Faced by Migrant Students in Education: A Comprehensive Analysis of Legal, Psychological, and Economic Barriers. Qubahan Academic Journal, 4(4), pp. 330-360.
6. . L Burkhanova [FOUNDATIONS FOR ESTABLISHING THE FACT OF THE UNKNOWN ABSENCE OF AN INDIVIDUAL UNDER THE CIVIL LAW OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN](#) Vol. 2 No. 4 (2023): [International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management](#)
7. Бурханова Л. М. ПУТЬ ЭВОЛЮЦИИ ИНВЕСТИЦИОННЫХ АКТИВОВ В МИРЕ И В РЕСПУБЛИКЕ УЗБЕКИСТАН //ББК 65.9 М34. – 2024. – С. 27.